

PAVE PACE
Concepts for Sensor Integration

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ABSTRACT

Future avionics sensor systems are the key to the advent of a multi-role fighter platform. The current cost, weight, volume, and power constraints limit the number and placement of sensors on weapon system platforms. In addition, the availability and performance issues associated with having a federated sensor system inhibit a multi-sensor weapon system. Next generation systems will be required to support A/A and A/G combat, defense suppression, and reconnaissance roles with little, if any, modification to the avionics equipment. In order to accomplish this, the current functional boundaries within the RF and EO arenas will need adjustment to better utilize the resources available.

PAVE PACE is an initiative in system avionics for the 21st century. One facet of the program is to explore the integration and architectural concepts that current sensor subsystems are driving towards and assess how future technologies will enable integrated sensor suites to become a reality. Several new technologies are evolving to allow this change in system design including wideband monolithic RF components, wideband fiber optic interconnections, highly programmable and higher performance signal processors, efficient multi-processor operating systems, multi-user broadband apertures, and artificial intelligence.

This paper will describe the challenges and issues in achieving an integrated sensor suite. It will describe the operational requirements that are necessitating the integration, the architectural concepts, and the technologies that need to be exploited to achieve such systems.

DISCUSSION

For the advent of a truly feasible Multi-Role Fighter (MRF), the ability of the avionics to perform all the functions necessary will be the critical element in a genuine multi-role weapon system. The requirement for functional flexibility will be increasingly important for future systems since shrinking

development budgets will preclude development of specialized platforms for individual tasks. Thus, we should expect the next generation systems to be required to support A/A and A/G combat, defensive suppression, and reconnaissance roles with minimal, if any, modification to the avionics equipment. Multi-role weapon systems with multi-role mission programmable avionics suites will be required.

COST, POWER, WEIGHT, RELIABILITY SHORTFALLS

In order to accomplish the functions necessary to complete all the varied multi-role mission segments, current sensor subsystems fall short in achieving the needed system goals in reliability, maintainability, performance, and cost. Figure 1 examines the avionics contributions by functional areas as a percentage of the total avionics system with respect to cost, power, weight, and reliability. What this figure shows is that the contributions to the system made by the sensors is far and above that made by the other avionics functional areas of Integrated Mission Processing (IMP), Pilot Vehicle Interface (PVI), Vehicle Management System (VMS), and Stores Management System (SMS). The MRF has been conjectured by the PAVE PACE program to have a fly away cost of \$20-25 Million (\$M). By estimating and using past experience, the avionics cost is roughly 30-40% of the flyaway costs or \$7.2 M. This cost has to encompass all the avionics functionality that is required to do the multi-role missions. As the previous figure indicates, sensor systems are roughly 50% of the total avionics cost. This means that in order to meet the cost goals needed for the weapon system platform, the sensor system must achieve a cost figure of around \$3.5 M! Figure 2 shows the consolidated Rough Order of Magnitude (ROM) costs, weight, volume, reliability, and power for the current federated sensor systems that would possibly be needed to accomplish a multi-role mission. These subsystem estimates are based upon current timeframe (1990) design approaches for the different sensor subsystems. What the previous estimates and figures illustrate is that there must be a well thought-out, orderly evolution to the way that sensor systems are being built if we are to advocate, afford, and maintain a true multi-role weapon system in the future.

AVIONIC CONTRIBUTIONS BY FUNCTIONAL AREA

Figure 1

Federated RF SubSystem Characteristics

Characteristic	ICNIA	INEWS	RADAR
Reliability MTBF (hrs)	360	394	968
Cost (1990 \$)	\$ 900 K	\$2.9 M	\$2.8 M
Power (watts)	800	4 K	30 K
Weight (lbs)	90	350	500
Volume (cu ft)	1.4	6.5	3.6

Federated EO System Characteristics

Characteristic	Navigational FLIR	Targeting FLIR	IRST	ESM (4)	Laser TD/R	Laser Warning (4)
Reliability MTBF (hours)	400	400	342	1100	1000	1000
Cost (1990 \$)	\$600 K	\$1.5 M	\$2 M	\$112.75 K	\$200 K	\$70 K
Power (watts)	1K	5K	725	400	100	400
Weight (lbs)	212	420	112	44	22	44
Volume (cu ft)	4.6	10	2.1	0.6	0.22	0.6

Figure 2

Although each of the functional sensor subsystem areas such as Communication, Navigation, Identification (CNI), Radar, Electronic Warfare (EW), and Electro Optic/Infrared (EO/IR) are pursuing advanced technologies and concepts to expand their performance and reliability parameters, the other system parameters of cost, weight, and volume of these subsystems cannot be achieved. Figure 3 illustrates this statement. The first bar on each of the graphs indicate the combination of federated sensor subsystem approaches as they are currently being demonstrated. As the graph indicates the cost of fielding the systems needed is estimated to be \$11.3 M. The second bar on each graph estimates the infusion that technology would have on upgrades of the current sensor subsystems. This assumes that there is a

"business as usual" attitude throughout the sensor subsystem developers and technology reuse is limited to its current state. For example, with the injection of some of the Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMIC) technologies and other technologies that naturally will come about, the sensor system reliability can be increased 10 hours and the weight can be decreased from 1918 lbs to 1571 lbs. With a consolidated effort of technology insertion coupled with a greater level of integration, a higher payoff could be achieved. The third bar on the graphs represents the progress of the PAVE PACE contractors in their design analysis of an Integrated Sensor System (ISS).

FIGURE 3 - SENSOR TRENDS

From the past examples it is easy to see that the level of integration being implemented has a tremendous impact on the cost, weight, power, volume, and reliability of the system being developed. Two factors contribute to the system designers ability to achieve this higher integration level; technology maturation and political/organizational structures. Knowing that technology will move forward and ultimately achieve the needed maturation level, it is important to consider the latter factor.

The level of sensor integration that each of the functional areas of Radar, EW, CNI, and EO/IR are pursuing do not promote a "system" level thrust in order to meet future weapon system goals. Political boundaries and organizational structures within the government and industry have dictated that each of the representative organizations focus their efforts and resources to achieve their particular applications goals. This has resulted in the formation of the federated integrated sensor subsystems throughout the avionics system (i.e., ICNIA, INEWS, URR, FLIR, IRST). Although these programs are highly successful and are the first steps towards an integrated sensor system, the cost, weight, volume, and power constraints limit their use on

a single platform. In order to meet our goals, the acquisition culture of weapon systems will have to change. The reality of company "X" building the RADAR, Company "Y" building the EW suite, and Company "Z" building the CNI suite for an aircraft prime contractor will need to be altered. This will only happen by the merging of the organization boundaries both within industry and within government.

ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The architectural design evolution that future sensor systems are moving towards is evident. The creation of super subsystems composed of RF and EO building blocks are emerging. Although common apertures and standard processing for EO apertures are emerging, with the payoffs equally as measurable, the current standardization and integration thrusts seem to focus on the RF arena.

The integration of RF sensor subsystems began with the promotion of a common module architecture using standard data and signal processors to accomplish the processing functions. These loosely coupled subsystems make up the bulk of the sensors being procured for the next set of military aircraft. As you can see from figure 4, the functional structure for the CNI, Radar, EW subsystems in front of the processing remains fairly traditional. The figure outlines the areas that seem to have a high degree of commonality among themselves. To this end, all the RF assets needed on-board share a common structure of an aperture tailored to an airframe, connected with a signal distribution

network to a set of analog processing channels. Up to now the degree to which these areas were common depended upon the specific requirements of the sensor and the level of technology available to implement that function over the frequency band required. But, technology is slowly allowing an architectural metamorphosis to take place.

Technological advances are allowing system designers to look at all the RF assets over the entire frequency range as "signals of interest" instead of specific frequency bands that have to be processed. Figure 5 illustrates the frequency coverage that needs to be "sensed" for the RF functions of Radar, CNI, and EW.

Figure 5

CNI Sensor Generic Block Diagram

Radar Sensor Generic Block Diagram

EW Sensor Generic Block Diagram

Figure 4 - Potential Integration Areas

One of the first architectural components that have to be in concert with this approach is the apertures. Conventional approaches utilize narrowband antennas to support a specific function or waveform. Considering the plethora of functions that need to be supported, the number of antennas on a particular platform can easily reach 30-40. For example, the F-4G "Wild Weasel" has roughly 44 different apertures. This large number of antennas impose interface and control complexity problems while also negatively impacting the platforms Radar Cross Section (RCS). Ideally one would like to have conformal multi-function antennas that have wide operating bandwidths and are capable of simultaneous operation of different waveforms. Also they must have the flexibility to reassign functions as required during different mission situations (failures, change of phases, etc.) in order to make efficient utilization of the antenna assets. However, the reality of what an antenna can accomplish must be traded off with the rest of the system. In evaluating the system level issues, consideration must be given to simultaneity issues, antenna type, and functional characteristics (i.e., frequency, polarization, field of view, required beamforming). For most Radar and CNI functions antenna gain and coverage must be considered with other performance parameters such as transmitter output power levels, system sensitivity, minimum required signal to noise ratios, and processing gains for each function in determining the effective range characteristics. However, EW antenna characteristics are specified in terms of emitter sensitivities, field of view, direction finding accuracy, and others.

Technology is pushing hard in the aperture area. The application of MMICs and Microwave and Millimeter Wave Integrated Circuits (MIMICs) in the entire RF sensor area is the focus of a tremendous amount of work throughout industry. MMIC utilizes silicon and Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) circuit technologies to combine individual components such as amplifiers, detectors, A/Ds, etc. in order to implement more complex subsystem components like Transmit/Receive (T/R) modules, receivers, etc. However, in the aperture area MMICs are providing the capability of the T/R modules that drive the power to the elements with the flexibility to operate over a much broader frequency band. Although promising work is being accomplished to increase the output power and efficiencies of the T/R modules, cost is still a prohibitive factor. Other technologies are being pursued as well in the aperture area. With the advent of broadband arrays, the radomes to support their integration with the airframe is a concern. Since radomes act as layers of dielectrics that react to changes in frequency and angle of waves incident upon them, finding the correct mix of responsiveness to their in-band and out-of-band operation across a very broad band is a challenge. Because steering and directionality are becoming more important even for functions (like CNI) which have classically been omnidirectional, techniques to control the

beamforming for the phased arrays are being pursued. Three possible approaches are: 1) phase shifters, 2) optical, and 3) digital. The merging of the apertures across the entire frequency band is the first step to achieving a totally integrated sensor system.

Analog designers have not had the ability to modularize because of the individual requirements for noise, bandwidth, and sensitivity of the specific functions. But, because of the advances of MMIC, the ability to standardize and modularize the receive and transmit portions of the sensor architecture are becoming practical. The receiver area holds great promise for commonality. The utilization of MMIC for a set of common receivers will do for the RF system what the VHSIC and common processors did for the central and signal processing. The ideal situation for processing the signals off the aperture would be to have a set of receivers/transmitters capable of covering the entire band of interest connected by a switching network to route the signals from the aperture to a signal and data processing system.

Figure 6 shows an implementation concept for an integrated sensor system that has been designed by TRW for the McDonnell Douglas PAVE PACE team. The signals are routed from the aperture to a broadband switch by the apertures electronics. The switch sends the signals to a set of frequency converters which convert the incoming RF signals to a common Intermediate Frequency (IF). A key consideration is to choose an IF which will neither cause a spurious response when mixed nor create an undesired coupling, and still accommodate all the different signal bandwidths of the functions of interest. Because of the diverse frequency band coverages needed, a decision for more than one IF might seem practical. Also, double conversion of the signal is an approach that could be taken if you are trying to stay at one IF. The IF selection is also dependent on the digitization approach available by the A/D conversion technology. After an up or down conversion depending on the signals frequency, the signals are routed to a set of receivers utilizing an IF switch network. The set of receivers could contain a minimum number of types of receivers to accommodate the various signals of interest. In most cases the routing of the signal is then carried to the high speed general purpose programmable processors. The necessity of a pre-processor to accomplish certain functions such as pulse detection, correlation functions, and matched filtering before being sent to a general signal processor is an architectural trade that needs to be further addressed. Although processing speeds have increased dramatically, certain operations such as spread spectrum pseudo-noise (PN) wipeoff and pulse processing will need dedicated preprocessor assets. The general architectural trend is to push the A/D conversion as close to the aperture as possible and try to modularize and standardize the receivers and processing.

Figure 6

Obviously in order to implement this kind of integrated RF architecture the appropriate technologies must be applied at a system level to achieve the payoffs that an ISS might afford.

SENSOR MANAGEMENT and SENSOR CONTROL

Hardware technology can eventually support an integrated sensor suite that has been discussed, but the key to achieving the benefits afforded by the hardware will be the software control and management of the system. The software development complexity and costs might preclude the cost benefits obtained by the integration of the hardware assets. Possible reuse of the software that is being developed for today's federated subsystems is not practical. Most of these subsystems perform a function or limited number of functions simultaneously, and each are tailored to optimize the performance of the subsystem for those functions. At most, some of the algorithms that have been developed could be reused. This is certainly a technology area that will need more research and development in the coming years. It is envisioned that the control of the ISS will need to support the real-time processing needs of the system as well as dynamically schedule and allocate resources based upon random events, known changes, and insufficient information. These requirements bring about several challenges. A significant challenge is the scheduling paradigm of the system. If the resources are to be time shared, there are problems associated with the contention of resources versus the functions desiring the resource at a specific moment in time. A scheduling algorithm to accommodate this type of real-time problem is being explored, but is still not well understood. This is especially true for scheduling algorithms that have to handle more than one resource at a time. Another challenge is the modelling, verification, and validation of the system. Today's modelling systems execute in the time domain and have difficulty modelling the size and complexity of the system that is being described. A potential problem in an integrated RF system will be the frequency contention and mixing associated with all the possible signals in the system. A careful frequency plan and fiber optics should contribute

to avoiding this problem. The problem with the verification and validation of this type of system will be the metrics that are used to evaluate all the possible combinations of sensor contentions and usages.

Figure 7 is a partial list of the types of tasks a sensor manager and sensor control function would need to accomplish. An example illustrates the benefits that a sensor manager would have. By utilizing a shared aperture, that could possibly be divided into subarrays, the sensor manager could direct the emissions of certain functions such as the radar, while using the other sections of the array to perform some sort of jamming functions. This would enhance the observable characteristics of the platform while providing a capability of using offensive and defensive assets concurrently that is not presently available.

POSSIBLE SENSOR MANAGEMENT AND SENSOR CONTROL FUNCTIONS

- CONTROL OF ALL RF ASSETS AND FUNCTIONS
- REAL-TIME OPERATION
- DYNAMIC RECONFIGURATION
- FUNCTIONAL FLEXIBILITY TO ALLOW DIFFERENT MISSIONS AND CREW SKILL LEVEL
- RESOURCE SCHEDULING
- FUSION OF ONBOARD AND OFFBOARD ASSETS

Figure 7

OPERATIONAL CONCEPTS

Consider the operational benefits of having an Integrated Sensor System (ISS). Normally on classical strike missions the number of assets required to penetrate the target would need to be roughly seven to nine. Two F-111's would be used to perform the A/G payload delivery, two F-15's would be used to provide the fighter escort, and a EF-111 would be used for standoff jamming support. Also, F-4G's would possibly be needed for the Suppression of Enemy Air Defenses (SEAD). By using the ISS approach utilizing the multi-function apertures, reconfigurable wideband resources, and sensor management schemes it would be possible to only utilize two to three assets. One asset, because of the ability to utilize a full aperture for a single function, could perform the standoff jamming function. Also, if this was a multiple strike one could even envision using this platform as a "mini" Airborne Warning and Control System (AWACS) to coordinate the attack. The other two assets could perform the penetration and SEAD missions. By dividing the apertures into subarrays, a number of the subarrays could be used for the escort jamming and the other part of the array could be used for target location.

SUMMARY

The diversity of the functions and sensor systems bring about numerous challenges for the scientific and technical communities. The potential payoffs in terms of cost, volume, weight, reliability, and operational benefits warrant a detailed design program to prove the various concepts and technologies. Although technology (software probably more than hardware) may limit the amount of integration that is ultimately achievable, it is clear that a consolidated system approach between the various technological and functional organizations involved is necessary.

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